

Influence of Elevated Temperature and Carbon Dioxide in Mustard Cultivars and its Effect on Crop Yield, Percentage Content of Nitrogen and Sulfur¹

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Abstract

The present study was conducted during rabi season in the year of 2022-23. The experiments were conducted in open top chambers established in the research area of Department of Environmental Science, College of Agriculture, RVSKVV, Gwalior have uniform topography and adequate drainage conditions. The trial was laid out in a two way factor anovawith three replications. It was consisting of five elevated/ambient temperature and carbon dioxide viz., T1-ambient in OTC+Ambient CO₂, T2-ambient+1°C+425 ppm, T3-ambient+1.5°C+450 ppm, T4-ambient+2°C+500 ppm, T5-Open field (control) and two mustard cultivars at varied crop geometry i.e., RVM2 (45x10cm & 25x20cm) and Giriraj (45x10cm & 25x20cm). Results indicated that significantly higher no. of siliqua per plant, no. of seed per siliqua, length of siliqua (cm), 1000 seed weight (g), total biomass (q/ha), seed yield (q/ha) and harvest index (%), nitrogen content (%) and sulfur content (%) was obtained at T2-ambient+1°C+425 ppm, which was significantly superior over rest of the elevated treatments and open field control (OTCs) conditions. The highest no. of siliqua per plant, no. of seed per siliqua, length of siliqua (cm), 1000 seed weight (g), total biomass (q/ha), seed yield (q/ha) and nitrogen (%) was observed with mustard cultivar of Giriraj (45x10 cm) mustard cultivar with spacing except harvest index (%) and sulfur (%), respectively.

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Keywords

Elevated temperature, ambient CO₂, RVM2, Giriraj, Open Top Chamber (OTC).

Introduction

The Brassicaceae, contains about 3500 species and 350 genera, is one of the 10 most economically important plant families. It is distinguished on the basis of the presence of Conduplicate cotyledons (i.e. the cotyledons are longitudinally folded around the radical) and/ or two-segmented fruits (siliquae), which contain seeds in one or both segments, and only simple hairs, if present. Crop brassicas include a wide variety of plants that are grown as vegetables, fodder, or as a source of oil and spices. There has been a huge expansion in the area of oilseeds in Rajasthan, Madhya Pradesh and Chhattisgarh. Rapeseed & Mustard contributed maximum in increasing oilseeds area during this *Rabi* season. Mustard area increased by 6.77 lakh hectares from 91.25 lakh hectares in 2021-22 to 98.02 lakh hectares in 2022-23. Thus, out of 7.49 lakh hectares increase in area under oilseeds, rapeseed & mustard alone accounted for 6.44 lakh hectares. The area brought under rapeseed and mustard cultivation is 54.51% more than the normal sown area of 63.46 lakh hectares. Mustard area in Madhya Pradesh is 1.23 million ha which is about 5.5% of the total net sown area. The production is 1.69 million tones with yield of 1376 kg/ha (Agricultural Statistics at a Glance 2022). The increase in atmospheric concentration of CO₂ is the main driver of global warming. According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, 2007), atmospheric CO₂ concentration has exceeded 400 parts per million (ppm) with a consequence of global temperature increase by 0.85°C since the industrial revolution. The atmospheric CO₂ concentration is predicted to reach 500~700 ppm by 2050 and 650~1200 ppm by 2100, which is likely to contribute to a global temperature increase of 2 to 4°C by the end of this century. In India several authors have shown that during last century increasing trend in surface temperature has been observed (Singh and Sontakke, 2002, Lenka *et al.*, 2017). Since Madhya Pradesh has large area under mustard so the present investigation is an attempt to analyze the effects of high temperature on seed yield and growth parameters of mustard cultivars under elevated temperature and ambient CO₂.

Application of sulphur was reported to increase yield attributes and yield of Indian mustard (Patel *et al.* 2009, Kumar *et al.* 2011), which also has a significant effect on oil, fatty acid (Ahmad and Abdin 2000) and glucosinolates content in mustard seed (Falk *et al.* 2007). The relative proportions of individual glucosinolates viz. sinigrin (allyl isothiocyanate), gluconapin (3-butenyl glucosinolate) and progoitrin (2-hydroxy-3-butenyl glucosinolate) are influenced by sulphur application (Hassan *et al.* 2007). Sulfur Fertilizer: Among the oilseed crops, rapeseed and mustard require the most sulfur. Sulfur promotes oil synthesis. It is an important component of seed proteins, amino acids, enzymes, glucosinolates and is essential for chlorophyll formation. Sulfur increased mustard yield by 12 to 48% under irrigation and by 17 to 124% under rainfed conditions. In terms of agricultural efficiency, each kg of sulfur increases the yield of mustard by 7.7 kg. Canola-4 and Hyola-401 have 3% more oil content than hybrid "PGSH-51" due to the effect of different doses of nitrogen and sulfur.

Due to its hardy nature and ability to thrive well under poor conditions of fertility and moisture, it is generally grown as a rain-fed crop, with a low average yield. Mustard is a crop of tropical and temperate regions. The temperature requirement ranges from 0.5-3.0°C (min) to 35-40°C (max) with an optimum temperature of 20-35°C. Oil yields are enhanced by cool temperatures, dry weather and a good amount of bright sunlight. Oil yields are enhanced by cool temperatures, dry weather and a good amount of bright sunlight. Mustard requires high temperature (20°C-32°C) for vegetative growth and cool temperature with clear sky during reproductive growth and maturity.

The production potential of Indian mustard can be fully exploited under these conditions with appropriate agricultural practices and varieties. The present investigation is an attempt to analyze the effect of elevated temperature and carbon dioxide in mustard cultivars and its effect on crop yield, percentage content of nitrogen and sulfur.

Materials and Methods

The experiment was carried out in open top chambers established in the department of environmental sciences at College of Agriculture, Gwalior during *rabi* season of 2022-23 having uniform topography and adequate drainage conditions. The Open top chambers (OTCs) were set up in order to examine the effect of elevated temperature on growth and yield of mustard cultivars, where the basic metal frame fitted in the field are covered by PVC (polyvinyl chloride) sheet to allow maximum natural light was open at the top. Gwalior is situated in Gird zone at the latitude of 26°13' North and longitude 76°14' East with an altitude of 211.52 meters from above mean sea level, in the Madhya Pradesh, India. The region comes under semi-arid sub-tropical climate with extreme weather conditions with hot and dry summer and cold winter which is also affected due to undergoing climate change pattern. Generally, monsoon sets in during the last week of June to the first week of July. Annual rainfall ranges from 700 to 800 mm, most of which falls during last June to the first fortnight of September. The maximum temperature goes up to 45-46°C during summer and minimum as low as 3.8°C during winter.

The OTCs are set up to confine the temperature and CO₂ gas around the experimental plants in order to examine the combined effect of temperature & CO₂ in the second *rabi* season 2022-23 on growth, yield and quality of mustard cultivars. Open top chambers are built with high quality multilayered UV protected 90% light transparent polycarbonate sheet 4-5 mm thickness and galvanized iron and hi-grade aluminum channel, circular type structure with top side partially open for the experimental purpose. Those chambers are designed for carbon di-oxide, ozone and the temperature elevation facilities and integrated with meteorological parameter, soil sensors, wireless communication and web based (GPRS) SCADA technology. OTC Diameter was Top height: 3.5 mtr, diameter 4.7 m, cylindrical shape, area: 15.8 m². Height adjustable, IR heater, Sensor box, Agitating Fans 4 nos. integration. Parameter measured inside OTCs are CO₂, O₃, temperature, RH, soil temperature. Anemometer, PAR, Pyranometer, Rain Gauge, soil sensor, ozone sensor and drip irrigation system for all OTC. The elevated CO₂ concentration inside the chamber was maintained by injecting CO₂ from the CO₂ cylinders every day of experimental period. CO₂ was supplied from 10:00 am to 5:00 pm per day during the experiment period.

The present experiment four open top chambers and one control plot were selected having the diameter of 4.7 m at the research farm of Department of Environmental sciences, Climate change project unit, College of Agriculture, Gwalior. The two mustard cultivars at varied crop geometry i.e., RVM2 (45x10cm & 25x20cm) and Giriraj (45x10cm & 25x20cm) were grown in the chambers as well as in the natural conditions. The different elevated temperature and CO₂ concentrations maintained in the open top chambers were 1st with ambient CO₂, 2nd with ambient + 1°C + 425 ppm, 3rd with ambient + 1.5°C + 450 ppm, 4th with ambient + 2°C + 500 ppm for the present study. Temperature was maintained in all the chambers with the help of infrared heaters having automation system in order to maintain the level of temperature under the research work. Two plots in each OTC of 2 m² areas were laid out in 3 replications having 8 plants of Brassica cultivars in each. The plants were tagged for sampling from each plot and each chamber. The plant growth observations were recorded at harvest stages. Plants were marked and tagged for data. The yield was measured at harvesting stage and all plants from each plot of 2 m² area were harvested to record yield. The data were statistically analyzed using two way factor analysis with replication to test the significance of elevated temperature and ambient CO₂ at 1% and 5% level of significance.

Results and Discussion

Yield parameters and Nitrogen, Sulfur percent content at harvest

Data was recorded in no. of siliqua/plant, no. of seed / siliqua, length of siliqua (cm), 1000 seed weight (g), total biomass (q/ha), seed yield (q/ha), harvest index (%), nitrogen (%) and sulfur content (%) as affected by elevated temperature and ambient carbon dioxide on yield and percent content of nitrogen and sulfur of mustard cultivars at varied crop geometry at harvest stages have been presented in Table 1.

(a) Elevated temperature and CO₂ levels

No. of siliqua/plant: The elevated temperature level with T2-ambient+1°C+425 ppm (178.57 siliqua/plant) attained significantly higher values of no. of siliqua per plant. The T4-ambient+2°C+500 ppm recorded (167.47 siliqua/plant) the significant reduction in the values of no. of siliqua per plant of mustard cultivars compared to other elevated temperature+CO₂ concentrations and open field (control) condition.

No. of seed/siliqua: The elevated temperature level with T2-ambient+1°C+425 ppm (20.62 seed/siliqua) attained significantly higher values of no. of seed per siliqua. The T4-ambient+2°C+500 ppm recorded (17.40 seed/siliqua) the significant reduction in the values of no. of seed per siliqua of mustard cultivars compared to other elevated temperature+CO₂ concentrations and open field (control) condition.

Length of siliqua (cm): The elevated temperature level with T2-ambient+1°C+425 ppm (6.13 cm) attained significantly higher values of length of siliqua. The T4-ambient+2°C+500 ppm recorded (4.72 cm) the significant reduction in the values of length of siliqua of mustard cultivars compared to other elevated temperature+CO₂ concentrations and open field (control) condition.

1000 seed weight (g): The elevated temperature level with T2-ambient+1°C+425 ppm (7.18 g) attained significantly higher values of 1000 seed weight. The T4-ambient+2°C+500 ppm recorded (6.14 g) the significant reduction in the values of 1000 seed weight of mustard cultivars compared to other elevated temperature+CO₂ concentrations and open field (control) condition.

Total biomass (q/ha): The elevated temperature level with T2-ambient+1°C+425 ppm (231.30 q/ha) attained significantly higher values of total biomass. The T4-ambient+2°C+500 ppm recorded (210.75 q/ha) the significant reduction in the values of total biomass of mustard cultivars compared to other elevated temperature+CO₂ concentrations and open field (control) condition.

Seed yield (q/ha): The elevated temperature level with T2-ambient+1°C+425 ppm (26.52 q/ha) attained significantly higher values of seed yield. The T4-ambient+2°C+500 ppm recorded (23.11 q/ha) the significant reduction in the values of seed yield of mustard cultivars compared to other elevated temperature+CO₂ concentrations and open field (control) condition.

Harvest index (%): The elevated temperature level with T2-ambient+1°C+425 ppm (11.46%) attained significantly higher values of harvest index at harvest stage. The T4-ambient+2°C+500 ppm recorded (10.96%) the significant reduction in the values of harvest index of mustard cultivars compared to other elevated temperature+CO₂ concentrations and open field (control) condition.

Nitrogen (%): The ambient + 1°C + 425 ppm CO₂ (T2) and ambient+1.5°C + 450 ppm CO₂ (T3) significantly influenced the nitrogen content wherein the highest reading had been observed in ambient + 1°C + 425 ppm CO₂ (T2) unit having averaged value of 1.87 percent and lowest nitrogen content reading had been recorded in ambient+ 2°C + 500 ppm CO₂ (T4) having averaged value of 1.60 percent at harvest.

Sulfur (%): The open field (control) (T5) and ambient in OTC + ambient CO₂ (T1) significantly influenced the sulphur content wherein the highest reading had been observed in open field (control) (T5) unit having averaged value of 17.39 percent and lowest sulphur content reading had been recorded in ambient+ 1°C + 425 ppm CO₂ (T2) having averaged value of 16.82 percent at harvest. However, the treatment of open field (control) (T5) and ambient+ 1°C + 425 ppm CO₂(T2) which was statistically same all other treatment at harvest.

These results are also in conformity with the findings of Prakash *et al.* (2017), Srinivasa *et al.* (2018), Maity *et al.* (2019), Yubiet *et al.* (2019) and Angadi *et al.* (2021).

(b) Mustard cultivars at varied crop geometry

The mustard cultivars at varied crop geometry (RVM2 and Giriraj) also exhibited significant differences on the growth and yield attributes at harvest stages.

No. of siliqua/plant: The mustard cultivars Giriraj (45x10 cm) performed best and highest values (172.92 siliqua/plant) of no. of siliqua per plant under all mustard cultivars at varied crop geometry.

No. of seed/siliqua: The mustard cultivars Giriraj (45x10 cm) performed best and highest values (19.69 seed/siliqua) of no. of seed per siliqua under all mustard cultivars at varied crop geometry.

Length of siliqua (cm): The mustard cultivars Giriraj (45x10 cm) performed best and highest values (5.64 cm) of length of siliqua under all mustard cultivars at varied crop geometry.

1000 seed weight (g): The mustard cultivars Giriraj (45x10 cm) performed best and highest values (6.51 g) of 1000 seed weight under all mustard cultivars at varied crop geometry.

Total biomass (q/ha): The mustard cultivars Giriraj (45x10 cm) performed best and highest values (220.70 q/ha) of total biomass under all mustard cultivars at varied crop geometry.

Seed yield (q/ha): The mustard cultivars Giriraj (45x10 cm) performed best and highest values (25.00 q/ha) of seed yield under all mustard cultivars at varied crop geometry.

Harvest index (%): A perusal of data showed that harvest index percentage was non-significant due to the mustard cultivars at varied crop geometry.

Nitrogen (%): The Giriraj (45x10cm) cultivar observed maximum nitrogen content of averaged 1.81 percent and minimum nitrogen content had been recorded in Giriraj (25x20cm) of averaged value of 1.67 percent. However, the Giriraj (25x20cm) which was at par with the combination of RVM2 (45x10cm) and RVM2 (25x20cm).

Sulfur (%): Giriraj (45x10cm) cultivar observed maximum nitrogen content of averaged 1.81 percent and minimum nitrogen content had been recorded in Giriraj (25x20cm) of averaged value of 1.67 percent. However, the Giriraj (25x20cm) which was at par with the combination of RVM2 (45x10cm) and RVM2 (25x20cm).

Similar results were also observed by Shivani and Kumar (2002), Singh *et al.* (2002), Kumar *et al.* (2004) and Prasad *et al.* (2020).

Conclusion

The revealed that among mustard cultivars (RVM-2 and Giriraj) at varied crop geometry differential response was seen under changing climate scenario. Mustard cultivars have depicted significant variation with respect to growth and yield aspects under *Rabi* season 2022 elevated temperature+CO₂ conditions and Giriraj performed well as compared to RVM-2. However, T₂-ambient+1°C+425 ppm lead to increased growth and development. It can be concluded from the research work that if there is an increase in the mean temperature of the earth in future by 1°C there will not be a significant effect on the growth of mustard cultivars RVM-2 and Giriraj. However, further studies are needed to investigate the effect of elevated CO₂ under higher temperature conditions.

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Table 1: Yield Attributes and Seed Yield of Mustard Cultivars Varied Crop Geometry as Influenced by Elevated Temperature and CO₂ (at Harvest Stages)

Elevated Temperature	No. siliqua /plant	No. of seed/ siliqua	Length of siliqua (cm)	1000 seed weight (g)	Total biomass (q/ha)	Seed yield (q/ha)	Harvest index (%)	Nitrogen content (%)	Sulfur content (%)
T1-Ambient in OTC+Ambient CO ₂	171.30	17.87	5.08	6.24	215.22	24.39	11.34	1.66	17.07
T2-Ambient+1°C+425ppm	178.57	20.62	6.13	7.18	231.30	26.52	11.46	1.87	16.82
T3-Ambient+1.5°C+450ppm	169.05	17.82	4.94	6.18	211.51	23.95	11.32	1.72	16.99
T4-Ambient+2°C+500ppm	167.47	17.40	4.72	6.14	210.75	23.11	10.96	1.60	17.02
T5-Open field (control)	171.30	19.56	5.99	6.24	216.07	24.87	11.51	1.71	17.39
S.E.(m)+	0.357	0.184	0.070	0.023	1.253	0.234	0.118	0.011	0.155
CD (at 0.05%)	1.022	0.526	0.201	0.065	3.588	0.670	0.339	0.031	0.443
Mustard cultivars with spacing									
RVM2 (45x10 cm)	170.76	18.27	5.35	6.34	213.66	24.23	11.33	1.68	16.78
RVM2 (25x20 cm)	170.19	18.18	5.06	6.36	214.82	24.26	11.29	1.69	16.95
Giriraj (45x10 cm)	172.92	19.69	5.64	6.51	220.70	25.00	11.36	1.81	17.42
Giriraj (25x20 cm)	172.29	18.47	5.44	6.36	218.70	24.78	11.29	1.67	17.08
S.E.(m)+	0.319	0.164	0.063	0.020	1.121	0.209	0.106	0.010	0.138
CD (at 0.05%)	0.914	0.471	0.180	0.058	3.210	0.599	NS	0.028	NS